

On-farm assessment of footpad dermatitis in turkeys

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Definitions and welfare impact

Footpad dermatitis (FPD) is a contact dermatitis of the plantar surface of birds' feet which can affect the skin but also subjacent tissues and show different severity grades (Stracke et al. 2021) (Figure 1). FPD is associated with abnormalities of the footpad, such as redness, swelling, hyperkeratosis, tissue necrosis, or ulcers. Footpad dermatitis is a common welfare issues in commercially reared turkeys and broilers, because its painful to the birds and the prevalence could be high (Weber Wyneken et al., 2015). For example, Allain et al. (2013) showed that 99.9% of feet from 60 turkey flocks were affected by footpad dermatitis.

There are several factors linked with FPD such as breed, age, diet or sex. Regarding the age of the birds, although the degree of severity of skin lesions is higher in older birds, a significant number of turkeys may have footpad surface alterations as early as 6 weeks of life (Krautwald-Junghanns et al. 2011) and even from 3 weeks with histopathological changes associated with FPD on footpads showing no visible skin lesions (Mayne et al. 2006). Regards to the sex of turkeys and FPD, turkey hens may experience more footpad injuries and with greater severity compared to turkey toms (Krautwald-Junghanns et al. 2011). This may be due to the higher density of hens per unit area (hens being lighter, their numbers are higher than those of toms on the same surface) and the higher amount of feces downgrading the litter. The wet litter is highly correlated with the severity of FPD (Mayne et al., 2007; Krautwald-Junghanns et al., 2011; Wu and Hocking, 2011; Weber Wyneken et al., 2015). Indeed, Mayne and colleagues (2007) showed that keeping turkeys on wet litter (only water with no excreta added to the litter) for more than 48h is sufficient to induce lesions to the toe pads and

footpad dermatitis. Hence, the litter moisture control is a major proxy to decrease the severity and prevalence of FPD in turkey flocks. Attention should be paid to drinker design and maintenance, the choice of litter materials, and the management of litter quality (removal of soiled litter, addition of fresh dry litter), as well as to relative air humidity and ventilation efficiency.

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Figure 1: Footpad dermatitis of a turkey

Legal requirements

Regulation 98/58 CE, Annex, point 4 « Any animal which appears to be ill or injured must be cared for appropriately without delay and, where an animal does not respond to such care, veterinary advice must be obtained as soon as possible. Where necessary sick or injured animals shall be isolated in suitable accommodation with, where appropriate, dry comfortable bedding.”

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Methods of assessment

Several FPD scoring systems exist in turkeys based on the surface of the foot affected and the nature of the lesions (Mayne et al. 2006; Mayne et al. 2007; Hocking et al. 2008; Allain et al. 2013). In available scoring systems, the evaluation of FPD is done only on the metatarsal pad of the turkeys, the digital pads being not considered. A 2021 study compared the scoring of the metatarsal pad to a full scoring (including digital pads assessment) and authors concluded that the evaluation of lesions on digits could improve the classical FPD evaluation (Stracke et al. 2021). However, this study focused on automatic slaughterhouse assessment (cameras) and it seems to be premature to include digital pads to the FPD evaluation in turkeys on-farm as the feasibility remains low in these conditions (heavy birds handling and manipulations). Indeed, FPD is usually assessed at slaughter to increase the feasibility (no turkey handling and manipulation). In this factsheet, the method of assessment described was initially foreseen for at-slaughter assessment but, as the scoring scale is relatively simple, the assessment could be done on living birds on-farm.

The scoring scale of Hocking et al. (2008), designed to be a Standard European scoring system can be used. It has 5 scores (Table 1 and Figure 2). To perform the scoring on farm, each assessed turkey should be gently held and the surface of the pad examined. The adhering litter and excreta should be removed carefully if necessary with the help of a water and a soft brush, not to confuse faecal staining with necrotic areas. Instead of only scoring the right foot as indicated originally by Hocking et al., both bird feet could be scored and the most affected foot kept for final evaluation (Toppel et al. 2019) of each individual.

Table 1: Footpad dermatitis scoring system designed by Hocking et al. (2008)

Description of lesions

Score 0: No external signs of FPD. The skin of the foot pad feels soft to the touch and no swelling or necrosis is evident.

Score 1: The pad feels harder and denser than a non affected foot. The central part of the pad is raised, reticulate scales are separated and small black necrotic areas may be present.

	<p>Score 2: Marked swelling of the foot pad. Reticulate scales are black, forming scale shaped necrotic areas. The scales around the outside of the black areas may have turned white. The area of necrosis is less than one quarter of the total area of the foot pad.</p>
	<p>Score 3: Swelling is evident and the total foot pad size is enlarged. Reticulate scales are pronounced, increased in number and separated from each other. The amount of necrosis extends to one half of the foot pad.</p>
	<p>Score 4: As score 3, but with more than half the foot pad covered by necrotic cells.</p>

Figure 2: Scoring system for footpad dermatitis from Hocking et al. (2008) with pictures taken by Jenny Stracke (Stracke et al. 2021)

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